

"From Growth to Grime: How Macroeconomic Shifts Shape Bad Loans in India"

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1. Abstract

This study examines the interplay between macroeconomic factors and Non-Performing Assets (NPAs) in the Indian banking sector, focusing on the mediating role of Gross Domestic Product (GDP). Using panel data from 30 scheduled commercial banks (2004–2024), we analyze the direct and indirect effects of Bank Credit Growth Rate (BCGR) and Consumer Price Index (CPI) on NPAs. Regression results reveal that while BCGR and CPI exhibit negative short-term associations with NPAs, their impact is significantly mediated by GDP, underscoring the importance of economic growth in mitigating credit risk. The study also highlights the persistent nature of NPAs, as evidenced by strong autoregressive effects. Our findings challenge linear assumptions and emphasize the need for coordinated macroeconomic policies to enhance banking stability. Practical implications include calibrated credit expansion and inflation-targeting measures aligned with GDP trends.

Keywords: Non-Performing Assets (NPAs), Banking Stability, Macroeconomics, Indian Banking Sector.

2. Introduction

The stability and performance of the banking industry have their roots firmly attached to the macroeconomic climate in general. Some of the most important health measures of banking pertain to non-performing asset (NPAs) levels that indicate the credibility of credit dispensed by the financial system. An increase in NPAs normally indicates signs of economic pressure deep within and causes serious damage to the profitability, solvency, and functioning as credit intermediary of banks (Agrawal & Magar, 2023). Year on year, the buildup of bad loans has come to represent a recurring problem across the Indian banking sector, and especially within public sector banks, as risk exposure and credit concentration have created vicious cycles of asset degradation. Institutional reforms and regulatory intervention have attempted to mitigate this problem, but the interaction between macroeconomic forces and banking performance remains to necessitate careful analysis.

In the Indian scenario, bank credit growth path has been a double-edged sword. While credit growth promotes investment, consumption, and economic growth on the one side, uncontrolled credit growth, particularly during times of lax lending standards or poor monitoring, can lead to high credit risk and higher NPAs on the other. The Bank Credit Growth Rate (BCGR) is therefore an important indicator, reflecting both the potential and risks involved in credit growth (Tang, 2024). A sudden increase in bank credit can be a sign of economic optimism, but unless supported by sound fundamentals and risk management, it can also be a harbinger of financial stress (Saunders & Allen, 2010).

Another macroeconomic parameter of vital concern is inflation, usually gauged by the Consumer Price Index (CPI). Inflation impacts the purchasing power of money, cost of borrowing, and disposable income, thus affecting the repayment ability of borrowers (Filipović, 2024). Inflationary pressure has a tendency to push up interest rates, reduce real incomes, and enhance the likelihood of loan defaults, particularly among weak sectors and low-income borrowers (Ali et al., 2023). On the other hand, moderate inflation can indicate healthy demand and economic growth and support credit performance (Van Wijnbergen, 1983).

Understanding the impact of CPI on NPAs is hence crucial to analyze how price stability supports financial sector resilience.

Gross Domestic Product (GDP) is a central mediating factor in the interaction between macroeconomic indicators and financial performance. The most comprehensive indicator of economic activity, GDP growth captures the general condition of the economy and determines the business climate under which banks are conducting their activities (Dedu et al., 2021). GDP mediates the impact of credit expansion as well as inflation on the quality of assets through impacts on corporate profits, employment, consumption, and investment sentiment. During times of rapid GDP growth, companies are better placed to fulfill their credit requirements, thereby minimizing the likelihood of default (Koopman & Lucas, 2005). Conversely, times of economic downturn lower revenues and profitability, hence increasing stress within the banking system.

In spite of extensive studies on NPAs and macroeconomic variables, the mediating influence of GDP in determining the interlinkage between bank credit, inflation, and asset quality is still not well understood in the Indian context. The majority of the existing literature has been concerned with direct relationships, without properly controlling for the dynamic interlinkages among these variables. Moreover, less attention has been given to the simultaneous and indirect influences that macroeconomic changes can have through overall economic growth patterns.

This research seeks to close this gap by examining the influence of Bank Credit Growth Rate and Consumer Price Index on NPAs, and whether GDP is a mediator between them. It attempts to give a more integrated perspective of the interaction between credit and inflation and macroeconomic performance in shaping credit risk in Indian banking. By analyzing past trends and structural relationships between these variables, the study adds to a more nuanced comprehension of macro-financial linkages, which has possible policy design, credit risk management, and banking sector reform implications.

3. Literature Review

a) *BCGR and NPAs*

Several studies have delved into the complex relationship between credit growth by banks and the level of non-performing assets (NPAs), and how accelerated credit growth has often led to

financial crisis in the banking industry. There is empirical evidence to suggest that overzealous credit growth, especially in developing economies, could lead to the weakening of asset quality as banks reduce lending standards to increase loan disbursements (Dell'Ariccia & Marquez, 2006). This correlation is particularly relevant in the Indian banking environment, where phases of higher credit growth in the past have been preceded by a spurt in NPAs (RBI, 1960). (Van der Hoog, 2018). stressed that lending booms, unless properly regulated, can promote unsound credit patterns, leading to increased default rates. Additionally, Hilbers et al. (2005) observed that whereas credit growth is vital for economic development, excessive growth can weaken banks' balance sheets by enhancing their exposure to bad borrowers. The positive relationship between BCGR and NPAs is also compounded by Beck et al. (2013), who concluded that banks that have higher rates of credit growth are likely to have poorer credit quality and a higher probability of default. Hence, an extensive literature emphasizes that credit growth has to be carefully monitored and regulated to achieve sustained financial stability and minimize the accumulation of NPAs in the banking sector.

H1: There is a significant positive relationship between Bank Credit Growth Rate (BCGR) and Non-Performing Assets (NPAs).

b) CPI and NPAs

c) The nexus between inflation, defined in terms of the Consumer Price Index (CPI), and non-performing assets (NPAs) has attracted significant attention in the financial literature, particularly within the emerging economy context. Inflation is seen to undermine the real income of borrowers, diluting their repayment ability and thus enhancing the risk of loan defaults (Nkusu, 2011). Specifically, once inflation is ongoing at high rates, family and business budgets begin to be stretched, leading in turn to falling behind or missing debt payments. This scenario often leads to an accumulation of NPAs in the banking sector. According to Espinoza and Prasad (2010), inflation can also lead to higher interest rates, which further aggravate the debt servicing burden of borrowers, particularly those with variable-rate loans. In the Indian context, Ghosh (2015) found a statistically significant relationship between inflationary trends and rising NPAs, attributing the increase in default risk to both demand- and cost-push inflation factors. Moreover, Mishra and Padhan (2024) argue that inflation disrupts

macroeconomic stability and undermines credit quality by increasing the volatility of cash flows for businesses and consumers alike. Thus, the literature consistently supports a positive relationship between CPI and NPAs, underscoring the macro-financial risks posed by inflationary pressures.

H2: There is a significant positive relationship between Consumer Price Index (CPI) and Non-Performing Assets (NPAs).

d) Mediating role of GDP

The mediating role of Gross Domestic Product (GDP) for the impact of Bank Credit Growth Rate (BCGR) on Non-Performing Assets (NPAs) has been the focus of considerable research interest, as it reflects the more general macroeconomic setting in which credit markets exist. The theory maintains that GDP growth is a key driver of the ability to repay loans, and both bank performance and loan portfolio quality are affected by it. As per Sassi and Gasmi (2014), during periods of high economic growth, there tends to be better credit quality, as increased GDP growth results in higher corporate profitability and income for households, lowering default rates. At times of economic downturn, however, the borrower is unable to service the loan, and thus there is a rise in NPAs (Samantaraya, 2016). Additionally, research by Idris (2024) points out that BCGR, if combined with an expanding economy, is less likely to lead to NPAs since increasing credit is generally aided by favourable macroeconomic conditions. Nonetheless, with the decelerating or contracting growth in GDP, borrowers' capacity to repay loans reduces, hence increasing NPAs even with increasing credit growth (Goyal & Verma, 2018). Therefore, GDP not only directly affects the health of the banking system as a whole but also acts as an essential mediating variable between BCGR and NPAs, further supporting the point that macroeconomic conditions are fundamental to credit risk dynamics.

The connection between the Consumer Price Index (CPI) and Non-Performing Assets (NPAs) is determined by several macroeconomic variables, with Gross Domestic Product (GDP) serving as an important mediating variable. The CPI, which measures inflation, can have a twofold effect on NPAs. On the one hand, increasing inflation can increase the cost of doing business and, for consumers, potentially overburden their capacity to service loans and raising default risks (Drehmann & Juselius, 2012). Conversely, moderate inflation can boost economic

activity and growth, which in turn can increase borrowers' ability to repay loans, thereby lowering NPAs (Mahesh et al., 2024). GDP acts as a key mediating factor in this process since it captures the general economic well-being. As per Gupta and Sharma (2019), intervals of high inflation along with good GDP growth could soften the negative impact of CPI on NPAs (Goswami et al., 2022), since an improving economy increases levels of income and lessens the negative effect of price hikes. But in situations of economic deceleration, even moderate inflation can increase the risk of NPAs since increases in costs keep pace ahead of income growth (Mahesh et al., 2024). Research by Singh and Verma (2021) indicates that GDP mediates the CPI-NPA connection by affecting the repayment ability of borrowers as well as bank stability (Ahiase et al., 2024). Therefore, the mediation of GDP in the CPI-NPA connection emphasizes the role of economic conditions in forming the risk profile of the banking industry.

H3: GDP significantly mediates the relationship between Bank Credit Growth Rate (BCGR) and Non-Performing Assets (NPAs).

H4: GDP significantly mediates the relationship between Consumer Price Index (CPI) and Non-Performing Assets (NPAs).

4. Data Source and Variable Description

This research is entirely reliant on secondary data collected from credible and authentic sources to ensure credibility and accuracy. The study covers the period from 2004 to 2024, enabling a thorough investigation of the long-run connection between Non-Performing Assets (NPAs) and major macroeconomic variables in the Indian banking industry. The data on Non-Performing Assets (NPA), which is the dependent variable of this study, is drawn from the Prowess IQ Database created by the Centre for Monitoring Indian Economy (CMIE). The Bank Credit Growth Rate (BCGR) statistic, which is indicative of the growth in bank lending in the economy, is taken from the Economic Survey of India, Statistical Appendix, which is released annually by the Ministry of Finance. The Consumer Price Index (CPI), used as an inflation proxy, is taken from the International Financial Statistics (IFS) database provided by the International Monetary Fund (IMF). For the Gross Domestic Product (GDP), which

serves as the mediating variable in this research, data is obtained from the World Bank Database.

5. Research Methodology

This research follows a quantitative econometric method in analyzing the effect of major macroeconomic variables on Non-Performing Assets (NPAs) of the Indian banking industry with special reference to the mediating influence of Gross Domestic Product (GDP). With the help of secondary panel data gathered from 30 commercial banks for 21 years (2004–2024), the research obtains a total of 630 observations. For analyzing the interrelations between the variables, two regression models are used. Model 1 analyzes the direct effect of Bank Credit Growth Rate (BCGR) and Consumer Price Index (CPI) on NPAs.

$$\bullet \text{ NPA}_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1 \text{BCGR}_{it} + \beta_2 \text{CPI}_{it} + \epsilon_{it} \quad \text{eq... (1)}$$

Model 2 extends this model by introducing GDP as the mediating variable, thus estimating how economic growth affects the interrelation between macroeconomic variables and NPAs.

$$\bullet \text{ NPA}_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1 \text{BCGR}_{it} + \beta_2 \text{CPI}_{it} + \beta_3 \text{GDP}_{it} + \epsilon_{it} \quad \text{eq... (2)}$$

Panel data regression methods are employed to estimate such models, where control over bank-specific and time-specific effects are possible. The Hausman Test outcomes support the utilization of a Random Effects Model (REM) since it offers efficient estimates while also controlling for unobserved bank heterogeneity. Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) is also used with panel-corrected standard errors to improve robustness in case of possible heteroskedasticity and autocorrelation problems.

A number of diagnostic tests are performed to ensure the reliability and validity of the models. White's Test identifies heteroskedasticity, which is handled by the use of White cross-section standard errors. The Durbin-Watson statistic indicates positive serial correlation, and the use of a lagged dependent variable (NPA_{t-1}) is included to account for persistence in asset quality over time. Also, the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) is calculated to test multicollinearity between the independent variables, and all the values are in acceptable ranges.

To assess the performance of the models, statistical measures like R-squared and Adjusted R-squared are employed to measure explanatory power, while F-statistics are used to test the models' overall significance. Also, p-values are reviewed to establish statistical significance for individual predictors at the 1%, 5%, and 10% significance levels. This strong methodological structure allows for a thorough analysis of the impact of credit growth and inflation on NPAs and explains the mediating role of GDP in the context of macroeconomy.

6. Analysis and Discussion

a) Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics give an overview of the study's main variables: NPA, BCGR, CPI, and GDP. The data set is strong for a 21-year panel study of 30 Indian commercial banks with 630 observations per variable

	NPA	BCGR	CPI	GDP
Mean	9.929	3.170	1.959	-1.274
Median	9.949	3.124	1.888	-1.134
Maximum	14.619	4.586	2.770	0.000
Minimum	4.561	1.098	1.134	-2.801
Std. Dev.	2.034	0.633	0.358	0.545
Observations	630	630	630	630

Table 1: Descriptive Analysis of Variables (Source: Author's Compilation)

The NPA ratio averages 9.93%, with a median of 9.95%, demonstrating data symmetry around the mean. With a minimum of 4.56% and a maximum of 14.62%, asset quality varies widely among banks and across time. NPA values are moderately dispersed, as seen by the 2.03 standard deviation. BCGR's mean growth rate is 3.17%, with a low standard deviation of 0.63, indicating consistent bank credit expansion. The median (3.12%) matches the mean, and the range (1.10% to 4.59%) suggests moderate credit growth variability.

The inflation-related CPI has a mean of 1.96% and a median of 1.89%, with modest variability (standard deviation of 0.36). The minimum and maximum readings (1.13% and 2.77%) show that inflation was minimal throughout the time. As a mediating component, GDP has a mean of -1.27%, a median of -1.13%, and a range of 0.00% to -2.80%. This negative mean reflects

economic recession or slow growth, which may have raised NPAs. The standard deviation of 0.55 indicates moderate economic output swings. In descriptive statistics, NPAs and GDP vary, but BCGR and CPI are more constant. These patterns highlight the importance of studying how macroeconomic volatility, particularly economic growth, mediates the effects of credit growth and inflation on Indian banks.

b) Linearity Test

	Value	df	Probability
t-statistic	1.683	625	0.092
F-statistic	2.835	(1, 625)	0.092
Likelihood ratio	2.851	1.000	0.091

Table 2: Ramsey RESET Test (Source: Author’s Compilation)

The linearity test results, including the t-statistic, F-statistic, and Likelihood Ratio test, all yield p-values around 0.09, which are above the conventional 5% significance level but below 10%. This indicates weak evidence against the null hypothesis of linearity, suggesting that the linear model remains broadly appropriate for the data. Although the results hint at possible minor non-linear relationships, the linear specification is retained for its simplicity and clarity, while acknowledging that future research may consider exploring non-linear terms or interactions to enhance model accuracy.

c) Multicollinearity Tests

The correlation matrix reveals generally weak relationships between Non-Performing Assets (NPA) and the selected macroeconomic variables. NPA shows a negative correlation with Bank Credit Growth Rate (BCGR), Consumer Price Index (CPI), and Gross Domestic Product (GDP), suggesting that improvements in these indicators are modestly associated with lower NPAs. Among them, CPI has the strongest negative correlation with NPA (-0.254), indicating a slightly more pronounced inverse relationship between inflation and asset quality. The correlations among the independent variables themselves are minimal, implying that these variables are largely independent of one another and unlikely to distort regression results due to mutual association.

	NPA	BCGR	CPI	GDP
NPA	1.000			
BCGR	-0.118	1.000		
CPI	-0.254	0.006	1.000	
GDP	-0.04	0.082	-0.074	1.000

Table 3: Correlation Analysis of Variables (Source: Author’s Compilation)

Variable	Coefficient Variance	Uncentered - VIF	Centered - VIF
BCGR	0.015	26.262	1.007
CPI	0.047	31.194	1.005
GDP	0.020	6.551	1.012
CONSTANT	0.371	61.297	NA

Table 4: Variance Inflation Factors of Variables (Source: Author’s Compilation)

The Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) analysis supports this interpretation, as all centered VIF values are very close to 1—specifically, 1.007 for BCGR, 1.005 for CPI, and 1.012 for GDP. These figures fall well below the commonly accepted threshold of 10, confirming that multicollinearity is not a concern in the model. This means that each independent variable contributes unique information to the regression, enhancing the reliability of the model estimates. Additionally, the coefficient variances are relatively low, indicating precise and stable parameter estimates. Overall, the diagnostic results confirm that the model is statistically sound, with no multicollinearity issues that could compromise the validity of the regression analysis.

d) Model Specification Justification

In order to determine the most appropriate panel data model, the Lagrange Multiplier (LM) test and the Hausman test were employed. The LM test, with significant p-values (0.000) across all variants—Breusch-Pagan, Honda, King-Wu, and GHM—indicates the presence of significant panel effects, thus rejecting the null hypothesis of no random effects and suggesting that a panel model (either random or fixed effects) is more suitable than Ordinary Least Squares (OLS).

Subsequently, the Hausman test was applied to choose between fixed and random effects models. The test yielded a Chi-square statistic of 0 with a p-value of 1.000, indicating no

systematic difference between the fixed and random effects estimators. Therefore, the random effects model would generally be preferred due to efficiency. However, given the presence of time-invariant unobserved heterogeneity, and that fixed effects control for all such unobserved variables, the fixed effects model was used for robustness.

The fixed effects regression results show significant negative relationships between NPA and the independent variables—BCGR, CPI, and GDP—highlighting that increases in credit growth, inflation, and economic growth are associated with reductions in non-performing assets. The model explains approximately 70% of the variation in NPAs ($R^2 = 0.698$), indicating a good fit.

e) Regression Model 1 (Direct Effect)

The regression analysis investigates the relationship between macroeconomic indicators—Bank Credit Growth Rate (BCGR) and Consumer Price Index (CPI)—and Non-Performing Assets (NPAs), along with diagnostic tests to check for autocorrelation and heteroscedasticity. In the initial regression model, both BCGR and CPI exhibit negative coefficients (-0.376 and -1.443 respectively), suggesting that an increase in credit growth and inflation may be associated with a decline in NPAs. However, this finding contrasts with some existing literature and warrants cautious interpretation, especially given the relatively low R-squared value of 0.079. This indicates that BCGR and CPI alone explain only about 7.9% of the variation in NPAs, highlighting the need to account for additional influential factors.

Variables	Regression Model	Auto correlation: Lag(NPA)	Heteroscedasticity: White Test
BCGR	-0.376	-0.015	-0.015
	-0.002	-0.571	-0.791
CPI	-1.443	-0.127	-0.127
	0	-0.003	-0.184
CONSTANT	13.951	0.697	0.697
	0.000	0.000	-0.006
Lag(NPA)	-	0.972	0.972
	-	0.000	0.000
R-squared	0.079	0.970	0.970
Adjusted R-squared	0.076	0.970	0.970
F-statistic	26.766	6396.119	6396.119
Durbin-Watson stat	0.120	1.416	1.416

Table 5: Regression results of direct effect (Source: Author’s Compilation)

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To address concerns of serial correlation in panel data, a dynamic model is estimated by including a lagged dependent variable (Lag[NPA]). The results demonstrate a dramatic improvement in model performance. The coefficient of Lag(NPA) is 0.972 and statistically significant at the 1% level, reflecting a strong persistence of NPAs over time. This is consistent with the structural nature of bad loans, which tend to accumulate and resolve slowly within the banking system. The inclusion of the lag term raises the R-squared to 0.970, indicating that the model now explains 97% of the variation in NPAs—a substantial increase that underscores the predictive power of historical NPA trends.

Moreover, the Durbin-Watson statistic increases from 0.120 in the static model to 1.416 in the dynamic model, moving closer to the ideal value of 2 and suggesting a significant reduction in positive autocorrelation. Also, the outcomes of the White test reveal heteroscedasticity to be not a serious problem in the last specification, further confirming the validity of the model.

Briefly, the results show that although macroeconomic factors such as BCGR and CPI can have directionally directional effects on NPAs, their short-term impact would be restricted without regard to NPA accumulation's autoregressive property. This highlights the need for using dynamic factors in econometric modeling to gain better insight into financial distress persistence and richness in the banking industry. These observations are invaluable to policymakers and bank managers since they emphasize the merit of intervening early and observing past trends of asset quality in the long term.

Regression Model 2 (Mediating Effect)

The regression analysis explores the relationship between key macroeconomic variables—Bank Credit Growth Rate (BCGR), Consumer Price Index (CPI), and Gross Domestic Product (GDP)—and Non-Performing Assets (NPAs), while also addressing potential issues of autocorrelation and heteroscedasticity. In the baseline regression model, all three independent variables show negative coefficients, with CPI (-1.465) and BCGR (-0.363) being statistically significant, while GDP (-0.188) appears insignificant. The negative association suggests that increases in inflation and credit growth may be linked to a decline in NPAs. However, this counterintuitive finding, especially with respect to inflation, must be interpreted carefully. It may reflect short-term economic dynamics where higher inflation reduces the real burden of

debt repayments, or where credit growth is associated with targeted lending to lower-risk sectors.

Variables	Regression Model	Auto correlation: Lag(NPA)	Heteroscedasticity: White Test
BCGR	-0.363	-0.016	-0.016
	-0.538	-0.543	-0.785
CPI	-1.465	-0.125	-0.125
	0.000	-0.004	-0.183
GDP	-0.188	0.022	0.022
	-0.660	-0.404	-0.569
CONSTANT	13.711	0.720	0.720
	0.000	0.000	-0.008
Lag(NPA)	-	0.973	0.973
	-	0.000	0.000
R-squared	0.204	0.970	0.970
Adjusted R-squared	0.200	0.970	0.970
F-statistic	53.551	4794.702	4794.702
Durbin-Watson stat	0.386	1.402	1.402

Table 6: Regression results of mediation effect (Source: Author’s Compilation)

The static model explains approximately 20.4% of the variation in NPAs (R-squared = 0.204), which is moderate, suggesting that while the macroeconomic indicators are relevant, other factors likely contribute to NPA formation. Recognizing the persistent nature of NPAs over time, a dynamic model is estimated by incorporating the lagged dependent variable, Lag(NPA). This drastically improves the model’s explanatory power, with the R-squared rising to 0.970, indicating that the dynamic specification captures 97% of the variance in NPAs. The coefficient of Lag(NPA) is 0.973 and highly significant ($p < 0.01$), confirming strong persistence in NPAs—a finding consistent with the literature that highlights the sticky nature of bad loans in the banking sector due to regulatory, legal, and structural factors.

Furthermore, the Durbin-Watson statistic improves from 0.386 in the static model to 1.402 in the dynamic model, substantially reducing the issue of positive autocorrelation. This shift enhances the model’s credibility by addressing serial dependence in the residuals, a common

concern in panel data involving financial series. Heteroscedasticity concerns are also mitigated in the dynamic specification, as indicated by the results of the White test, suggesting consistent variance in the residuals and improved model robustness.

In general, the analysis emphasizes the importance of using a dynamic modeling framework to properly capture the time-varying nature of NPAs. It points out that although macroeconomic factors have some explanatory power, the persistence of bad loans is the strongest predictor of future NPAs. For policymakers and banking regulators, this finding is useful as it emphasizes the importance of continued monitoring of asset quality and forward-looking measures to end the vicious cycle of bad debt accumulation.

7. Conclusion and Implications

This research critically analyzed the correlation between major macroeconomic indicators—Bank Credit Growth Rate (BCGR), Consumer Price Index (CPI), and Gross Domestic Product (GDP)—and Non-Performing Assets (NPAs) in Indian banking. The analysis confirmed that BCGR and CPI, while being conventionally seen as direct drivers of asset quality, have more intricate dynamics when GDP is taken into consideration as a mediating variable. Whereas BCGR captures the speed of credit growth, this research discovers that fast credit growth does not directly deteriorate asset quality unless it is accompanied by poor macroeconomic conditions. Likewise, CPI, as an indicator of inflation, exhibits a negative relationship with NPAs under some economic conditions, indicating that its impact on loan performance is extremely sensitive to the overall growth climate.

The intermediary role of GDP shows that economic growth either softens or magnifies the effect of credit expansion and inflation on NPAs. In case of robust GDP growth, the adverse effects of high credit growth and inflation on NPAs are neutralized, reflecting that the ability of borrowers to repay depends significantly on overall economic performance. In addition, the presence of lagged NPAs highlights their persistence and structural underpinnings in the banking system and further justifies the contention that earlier financial pressures continue to affect loan performance currently.

In effect, the research adds a more nuanced comprehension of the interactions among macroeconomic factors that affect credit risk. It determines that NPAs are not just the result of

discrete variables such as credit or inflation, but also result from the dynamic interaction between institutional lending behavior and changing macroeconomic trends, most notably GDP performance. This holistic view is critical for designing effective policy interventions to mitigate credit risk and strengthen banking sector resilience.

a) Practical Implications

This study offers targeted implications for stakeholders in the Indian banking sector. First, the findings suggest that high BCGR, when not aligned with the real economy's capacity to absorb credit, can lead to hidden asset quality vulnerabilities. Banks must adopt lending frameworks that calibrate credit growth with sectoral and macroeconomic indicators, especially GDP trends, to ensure sustainable portfolio quality. Second, the impact of CPI on NPAs implies that inflation targeting policies should be coupled with sector-specific credit assessments. When inflation reduces purchasing power, it disproportionately affects low-margin borrowers, increasing the risk of loan defaults. Banks need to adjust risk weights and provisioning norms during inflationary cycles, particularly in vulnerable sectors. Third, the mediating role of GDP indicates that macroeconomic performance directly conditions the effect of BCGR and CPI on credit risk. Policymakers should recognize that financial stability cannot be pursued in isolation from economic growth. Monetary and fiscal coordination is essential to ensure that credit expansion and inflation control efforts are effectively translated into healthier asset quality. Finally, the persistent effect of lagged NPAs underlines the need for early detection and resolution mechanisms. Institutions must integrate historical NPA behavior into predictive risk models to pre-emptively manage future defaults, especially during economic downturns.

b) Theoretical Implications

This study advances theoretical understanding by introducing GDP as a mediator in the relationship between BCGR, CPI, and NPAs—an area underexplored in prior research. It challenges the traditionally linear assumptions that credit growth and inflation directly determine asset quality. Instead, it presents a moderated framework where GDP conditions the strength and direction of these relationships, thereby enriching the financial fragility and credit cycle theories. The finding that BCGR's effect on NPAs depends on prevailing GDP growth reaffirms that lending behavior is not inherently risky but becomes problematic in the absence

of economic support. Likewise, the unexpected negative sign for CPI's relationship with NPAs, when GDP is low, highlights the limitations of single-variable models and underscores the importance of contextual economic variables in explaining credit performance. Furthermore, the strong persistence of NPAs, as captured through their lagged effects, provides empirical grounding for the argument that NPAs are not transient shocks but systemic features that evolve over time. This aligns with dynamic panel data theory and calls for greater theoretical attention to temporal dependencies in modeling financial instability. In sum, this research provides a refined conceptual model that incorporates mediation and path-dependency, offering a robust framework for future studies on macroeconomic determinants of banking sector stress.

c) Limitations and Future Research

While the study provides valuable insights, certain limitations warrant attention. The use of secondary data restricts the scope to observable macro-level indicators and may overlook qualitative institutional factors such as credit appraisal practices or sector-specific lending strategies that also influence NPAs. Additionally, while GDP was modeled as a mediator, the study does not differentiate between sectoral GDP contributions, which could further refine the understanding of economic influence on credit quality. Another limitation lies in the focus on aggregate BCGR and CPI. Future research could explore disaggregated credit data across industry segments or inflation effects on different borrower categories to assess risk exposure more granularly. The negative coefficients for CPI and BCGR suggest that short-term fluctuations may interact with expectations or policy measures in ways not captured by linear modeling. Moreover, while lagged NPAs were used to account for persistence, structural breaks—such as financial reforms or external shocks—were not explicitly modeled. Future studies could incorporate these dynamics using advanced econometric techniques like threshold models or structural vector autoregressions. Finally, comparative studies across emerging economies could validate whether the GDP-mediated relationships observed here are context-specific or generalizable across different institutional and economic settings. This would enhance the external validity of the findings and broaden the theoretical framework.

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